

THE TOUGHNESS OF EPOXY POLYMERS AND FIBRE COMPOSITES MODIFIED WITH RUBBER MICROPARTICLES AND SILICA NANOPARTICLES

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1 General Introduction

Previous work using silica nanoparticles has shown that they can increase the toughness of epoxy polymers, and also increase their cyclic-fatigue performance [1,2]. The toughening mechanisms have been previously reviewed and identified [2]. However, with such tougheners the measured increases in the fracture toughness are relatively small compared to those that can be achieved using phase-separable rubbers, e.g. [2]. Notwithstanding, in the case of fibre-composites, often a relatively small increase in the toughness is all that is needed to ensure the successful application of the composite material. Since, (a) a small increase in the matrix toughness may be sufficient to stop microcracking during manufacture of the fibre-composite component, and/or (b) other toughening mechanisms such as fibre-bridging may also enhance the toughness of the fibre-composite compared to that of the bulk polymer matrix. Finally, and most noteworthy, the combination of a phase-separable rubber (with a resulting particle diameter of the order of micrometres) together with the silica nanoparticles, to give a 'hybrid' toughened epoxy, has been shown to give a synergistic toughening effect in the bulk epoxy polymer [3], i.e. the measured fracture energy is greater than the sum of the individual toughening effects from the two types of particle. Thus, these 'hybrid' epoxy polymers may indeed possess a very high level of toughness. The present paper extends these studies to composite materials and investigates the role of silica nanoparticles in an anhydride-cured epoxy polymer in bulk and when used as the matrix of carbon- and

glass-fibre reinforced composites. The formation of 'hybrid' materials, using a carboxyl-terminated butadiene-acrylonitrile rubber toughener together with the silica nanoparticles, is also discussed. The present work also extends a previous [2] model to predict the toughening effect of nanoparticles in a thermoset matrix.

2 Experimental

2.1 Bulk Materials

The materials were based upon a single-component hot-cured epoxy formulation. The epoxy resin was a standard diglycidyl ether of bis-phenol A (DGEBA) with an epoxide equivalent weight (EEW) of 185 g/eq, 'LY556' supplied by Huntsman, UK. The reactive liquid carboxyl-terminated butadiene-acrylonitrile (CTBN) rubber (which gives rise to micrometre-sized particles upon curing) was obtained as a CTBN-epoxy adduct with a rubber concentration of 40 wt.% in a DGEBA epoxy resin, namely 'Albipox 1000' (EEW = 330 g/eq) from Nanoresins, Germany. The silica (SiO₂) nanoparticles were obtained at a concentration of 40 wt.% in a DGEBA epoxy resin (EEW = 295 g/eq) as 'Nanopox F400' from Nanoresins. The curing agent was an accelerated methylhexahydrophthalic acid anhydride, 'Albidur HE 600' (AEW = 170 g/eq), also supplied by Nanoresins. The DGEBA epoxy resin was mixed with the epoxy containing the silica nanoparticles and/or the CTBN-epoxy adduct to give the required levels of silica nanoparticle and/or rubber modification. A stoichiometric amount of the curing agent was added to the mixture, which was stirred thoroughly and

degassed at 50°C and -1 atm. The resin mixture was then poured into a release-agent coated steel mould to produce plates from which bulk specimens could be machined. The specimen plates were cured at 90°C for 1 hour and then post-cured at 160°C for 2 hours. The compact tension specimens produced were used to determine the values of the fracture energy, G_C , of the bulk epoxy.

2.2 Composite Laminates

The modified matrices were infused into the fibre-reinforced composite systems; and both glass-fibre reinforced-polymer (GFRP) and carbon-fibre reinforced-polymer (CFRP) composites were studied. Unidirectional and quasi-isotropic GFRP panels were manufactured using a resin infusion under flexible tooling (RIFT) method. Unidirectional (UD) GFRP composites were produced using 'UT-E500' from SP Systems, UK, to produce 12 ply, 6 mm thick composites with a poly(tetrafluoroethylene) (PTFE) insert placed in the mid-plane to initiate a starter crack. Quasi-isotropic (QI) plates, 4 mm thick, were prepared using 8 plies of a biaxial stitched non-crimp fabric, 'XE450/1200' supplied by SP Systems, UK. These were laid up in a balanced symmetric lay-up to give a '0/0' interface across the fracture plane. A natural pre-crack was again initiated via a PTFE insert film. The CFRP panels were manufactured from a woven-fabric mat using a vacuum-assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM) method. These were produced by stacking a linen-weave '0/90' fabric mat supplied by Lange-Ritter, Germany, again with the addition of a PTFE insert to initiate the starter crack. The composite panels were cured under the same cure regime as the bulk epoxy polymer. Double-cantilever beam specimens were cut from the composites sheets and used to determine the interlaminar fracture energy, G_C (composite), of the composites.

3. Results and Conclusions

The structure/property relationship of an anhydride-cured epoxy modified with silica nanoparticles and/or rubber microparticles has been investigated. Microscopy showed that the silica nanoparticles were well-dispersed in the epoxy. However, in the 'hybrid' epoxy-polymer, which contained both silica nanoparticles and rubber microparticles, some

agglomeration of the silica nanoparticles was observed. The fracture energy, G_C , of the bulk epoxy polymer was increased from 77 to 212 J/m² by the addition of 20 wt.% silica nanoparticles. The observed toughening mechanisms were debonding of the epoxy polymer from the silica nanoparticles, followed by plastic void growth of the epoxy. Localised plastic shear-banding in the polymer was also observed. The largest increases in toughness were from the formation of the 'hybrid' epoxy polymers, which contained both silica nanoparticles and rubber microparticles, and here a maximum fracture energy of 965 J/m² was measured. The increases in the toughness of the bulk epoxy polymers were transferred to the fibre composites; and the interlaminar fracture energy, G_C (composite), of the fibre-composites was typically even further enhanced by fibre bridging, fibre debonding and fibre pull-out mechanisms coming into play for the composite materials. A previous model has been extended to predict the toughening effect of silica nanoparticles in a thermoset polymer to include the effects of shear banding, as well as plastic void growth of the epoxy polymer. There was excellent agreement between the predictions and the experimental data for the epoxy polymer containing silica nanoparticles. This model has also been used to predict the toughness of an epoxy containing micrometre-sized glass particles, and again good agreement was observed compared to the experimental data. Finally, both the theoretical and experimental studies clearly reveal the benefits of using silica nanoparticles, as opposed to much larger micrometre-sized silica particles, in terms of observing a relatively high toughness for the modified epoxy polymer and resulting fibre-composite.

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THERMAL BEHAVIOUR OF GLASS FIBRE INVESTIGATED BY THERMOMECHANICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

A TMA procedure has been developed with the capability of probing the thermal behaviour of glass fibre. A single glass fibre was successfully mounted into TMA fibre configuration and several thermomechanical programmes were carried out over a wide temperature range from 20°C to 900°C. It was found that measured coefficient of linear thermal expansion (CLTE) of boron-free E-glass fibre remained constant below 300°C and the values had an excellent agreement with that found in the literature. At higher temperatures an abrupt length change in glass transition region allowed for the determination of glass transition temperature (T_g). The results from isothermal measurement showed significant fibre length shrinkage, which was a function of both temperature and time. It follows that there exist two mechanisms, thermal expansion and structural relaxation, which together account for overall thermomechanical responses of glass fibre. The former is related to the decrease of Young's modulus at elevated temperatures and the latter is considered responsible for the observed increase of room temperature Young's modulus after thermally conditioning glass fibre at various temperatures.

Keywords: Glass fibre; Thermal analysis

1. Introduction

Glass fibre has been widely known as an engineering material that exhibits high specific

performance to cost ratio which accounts for its current dominant role in serving as the major reinforcement material for the global composite market. Parallel with this achievement there has been a great deal of the research and development effort devoted to this material over the past decades. Much of this work has been focused on fibre strength and fibre surface due to its reinforcement nature and the importance of fibre-matrix interaction [1-5]. It is well known that most composites are fabricated at elevated temperatures up to 300°C. Nevertheless the glass fibre is normally regarded inert at these temperatures and it is assumed that its physical and chemical properties remain independent of temperature and time. More recently, the growing trend and increasing interest of recycling end-of-life composites may impose much higher temperatures (e.g. 300°C–800°C) on glass fibres to enable their recovery for second-life use[6-8]. Therefore, it is of both scientific and technological importance to inspect the thermal behaviour of the glass fibre over a wide temperature range.

The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) is one of the most fundamental thermomechanical characteristics of a material and is determined by the composition and structure of the material. The definition of average CTE in length of a fibre, more usually known as coefficient of linear thermal expansion (CLTE), α_f , can be expressed as:

$$\alpha_f = \frac{\Delta L_f}{\Delta T \times L_f} \quad (1)$$

where ΔL_f is the change in length of the sample resulting from change in temperature ΔT and L_f is original length in the direction being measured. Three of the main techniques typically used for CLTE measurement of rigid solids are dilatometry, interferometry, and thermomechanical analysis (TMA). Despite the longstanding availability of these methods, studies of the CLTE of glass fibre are rather scarce. The literature survey on this subject usually leads to two main research categories. One involves thermal expansion behaviour of bulk glass with different compositions and structure [9-11]. The other usually concerns development of models for estimating CLTE of oxide glasses from their constituents [10, 12, 13]. Villeneuve et al. employed a gold-coated E-glass fibre to validate the measurement of thermal expansion by a TEM procedure [14]. Thermal strain of the coated E-glass fibre were determined at 200°C, 400°C, and 600°C and results showed that the difference between the experimental data and the theoretical straight lines drawn from the values of the CLTE in the literature became noticeable as the temperature increased [14].

Direct evaluation of fibre length change at several different temperatures was carried out by Otto [15], who attributed the observation of the length change to two competing mechanisms, namely thermal expansion and structural compaction. The latter was supported by the measurement of several physical properties including density, refractive index, and Young's modulus. Not much work has followed since then until recently structural change in glass fibres after heat-treatment below T_g was intensively studied by Yue et al [16-18]. This structural change has been identified as one of factors responsible for strength loss of thermally treated glass fibres [18, 19].

In the present work, we aimed to study the thermal behaviour of glass fibres by developing a protocol in a commercial TMA. The established procedure allowed us to characterise the CLTE and T_g of glass fibre over a broad temperature range from 20°C to 900°. The effect of thermal compaction was also investigated by the characterisation of isothermal change in fibre length and longitudinal modulus after heat treatment. Furthermore, the temperature dependence of Young's modulus was obtained for glass fibres and compared with the change of the modulus of heat-treated glass fibres.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Boron-free E-glass fibres supplied by Owens Corning Vetrotex were investigated in this work. All fibre rovings were produced on the same pilot scale bushing and were received as 20 kg continuous single end square edge packages. The rovings had a nominal tex of 1200 and a single fibre diameter of $17.4 \pm 1.3 \mu\text{m}$ [1]. The molten fibres had all been hyperquenched by water spray before they were coated with a normal rotating cylinder sizing applicator containing a 1% γ -aminopropylsilane (APS) hydrolysed solution in distilled water. All fibre packages were subsequently dried at 105°C for 24 hours. The room temperature mechanical properties of these fibres have been reported in somewhere else [1].

2.2 TMA procedure for glass fibre

Thermomechanical analyser Q400 manufactured by TA Instruments was used to measure length change of glass fibres as a function of temperature and time. The working mechanism of a typical modern TMA has been described in detail by other authors [20]. The key components in a TMA include a furnace system for providing a well-controlled test environment, stage/probe assembly for holding the specimen, and movable-core linear variable differential transducer whose output is

proportional to displacement of the core caused by changes in specimen dimension. Other important components involve a temperature sensor that can be placed in close proximity to the specimen and an electromechanical coil that can apply force to the sample.

Film or fibre samples are typically handled by a TMA with a stage-probe configuration as shown in Figure 1. This system consists of concentrically installed stage and probe. The former is fixed on a flat platform, while the inner probe is attached to a movable core of LVDT and can be driven up and down by a stepper motor. Both the stage and the probe have a 1.2 mm slot on the top for supporting upper and lower sample holders. Films may be secured with a pair of stainless steel clamps and fibres may be gripped by cleaved aluminium balls. Although such clamping mechanisms usually work well with tough materials, for instance, polymers and natural fibres, it proved not useful in this work as brittle glass fibres simply could not survive this process. Moreover, the low compliance of both metal clamps and glass fibres means a poor contact between them and is unlikely to prevent sample slipping during heating. Single glass fibre is often secured on mounting tabs using various adhesives (for example, epoxy, red sealing wax, and gel superglue) as in a standard single fibre tension test. The problems of using these adhesives include low heat resistance, much higher CTE than glass, and strong temperature dependence of stiffness. Phosphate cement (Electrotemp cement No.8 supplied by Glassbond Ltd) was, therefore, selected to serve as the sample holder. It could turn into a paste when it was mixed with water. The operator had sufficient time (~30 min) to embed both ends of a single fibre in the paste before it became solidified. A special jig was manufactured to ensure that both sample holds had flat and parallel surface. The original fibre length between sample holds was in a range from 19

mm to 23 mm. The sample was then left overnight at ambient temperature to allow the cement to fully set. The dry set cement has very low expansivity ($CLTE=4.7 \mu\text{m}/(\text{m}\cdot^{\circ}\text{C})$) and excellent heat tolerance (melting temperature $>1426^{\circ}\text{C}$) according to the datasheet from the supplier. Furthermore, phosphate cement was expected to form a strong bonding with glass fibre and secure the fibre throughout the entire heating process. The sample was mounted into fully calibrated TMA and the alignment of the fibre between the stage and the probe was achieved by the following steps: (1) placing the upper sample holder on the stage, (2) leaving the sample to hang freely, and (3) bringing the probe down to the lower sample holder by registering the initial fibre length. 10 mN static load, F_f , was applied to put the sample under slight tension and the load resulting from lower sample hold was negligible at relatively low temperature. The actual experimental set-up for the measurement with a single fibre is presented in Figure 1. A thermocouple was positioned near the middle of the fibre to monitor the temperature in the sample.

Several TMA programmes were carried out in the present work to study thermal behaviour of glass fibre. In order to characterise CLTE and T_g , samples were heated from 20°C to 900°C under nitrogen at a flow rate of 50ml/min. Different heating rates were used to demonstrate their influence on the measurement. To investigate the effect of temperature on structural changes in glass fibre, samples were kept at a range of elevated temperatures and isothermal length changes were measured as a function of time. In addition, Young's modulus of glass fibre was measured either at different temperatures from 20°C to 700°C with an increment of 20°C or at the room temperature after heat-treatment for 30 minutes from 50°C to 650°C with an increment of 50°C . The modulus was obtained from stress-strain curves

generated by a force ramp at a rate of 5mN/min until 20mN is reached.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 CLTE, Tg, and viscosity

Figure 2 presents a typical plot of length change measured as a function of temperature by the TMA procedure developed in this study. It can be seen that the glass fibre expands linearly at relatively low temperatures and gradually develops a varying expansion rate at high temperatures. Further increase of the temperature eventually leads to an abrupt change in the fibre length at glass transition region. The glass transition temperature, Tg, can be obtained by the point of intersection of the tangents to length versus temperature curve before and after the glass transition as shown in Figure 2. The steepest segment after Tg inevitably terminates with a sudden sharp inflexion followed by a continuous horizontal trace, which was not included in Figure 2. This is due to the fact that the sample length has exceeded the limit of travel distance of the inner probe and the omitted part is, thus, the signal of no interest.

It is usually recommended that when the materials with relatively low CLTE are measured using the TMA, apparent length change should be corrected for the dimensional change resulting from probe/stage fixture. In this work, the correction was carried out by taking into account the probe/stage inside the furnace as shown in Figure 1. The observed length change, ΔL , over ΔT can then be calculated by

$$\Delta L_{app} = \Delta L_f + \Delta L_p - \Delta L_{s1} - \Delta L_{s2} \quad (2)$$

and the actual length change in the sample can be expressed by

$$\Delta L_f = \Delta L_{app} - (\Delta L_p - \Delta L_{s2}) + \Delta L_{s1} \quad (3)$$

where L_f , L_p , L_{s1} , and L_{s2} are the length of the corresponding parts shown in Figure 1. $\Delta L_p - \Delta L_{s2}$ in Equation 2 can be replaced by length change, ΔL_b , measured in a blank run without the specimen during ΔT and $\Delta L_{s1} = L_f \alpha_s \Delta T$, where α_s is the CLTE of the stage used in TMA. The Equation 2 then becomes

$$\Delta L_f = \Delta L_{app} - \Delta L_b + L_f \alpha_s \Delta T \quad (4)$$

Since the 10 mN static force acts on the specimen throughout the test, the additional length change caused by the compliance change in glass fibres during the period of heating should also be considered. The compliance change of the glass fibre has been investigated by characterising Young's modulus of the glass fibre as a function of temperature using the same TMA and is discussed in the next section. Furthermore, the length change can be affected by the change in cross-sectional area of glass fibres due to thermal expansion and Poisson effect. However, these factors can be neglected for a thin fibre at relatively low temperatures (e.g. <400°C). The length change, ΔL_c , caused by the change of fibre compliance at relatively low temperatures can be estimated by

$$\Delta L_c = \frac{F_f L_f}{A_f} \left[\frac{1}{(E_f - \Delta E_f)} - \frac{1}{E_f} \right] \quad (5)$$

where E_f and ΔE_f are the fibre modulus at 20°C and the change in modulus over ΔT . Therefore, the more realistic ΔL_f may be obtained from the combination of Equation 3 and 4,

$$\Delta L_f = \Delta L_{app} - \Delta L_b + L_f \alpha_s \Delta T - \Delta L_c \quad (6)$$

The corrected plot of typical length change versus temperature was inserted in Figure 2. A closer inspection of the corrected plot revealed that the deviation from the linear relationship tends to become observable between 300°C and 400°C, above which the slope of the curve (i.e.

the instant CLTE) starts to decrease with the temperature before it increases as the temperature is approaching the glass transition. It is, thus, fair to say that the glass fibre may hold a constant CLTE up to 300°C and according to the definition expressed by Equation 1, the average CLTE can be obtained by the slope of the linear line fit to the curve. The decrease of CLTE is related to the effect of structural relaxation, which will be discussed later. Table 1 summarise the results of CLTE and T_g obtained for a number of individual glass fibres up to 300°C at the heating rate of 5°C/min. It is not reasonable to assume that all the fibres would have the same CLTE and T_g as it is impossible not to have somewhat inter-fibre variation in the composition and thermal history. Nevertheless, the coefficient of variation for both parameters is very low with 6% and less than 1% for the CLTE and T_g respectively. The correction was carried out by Equation 5 and $\alpha_{\text{stage}}=0.52 \mu\text{m}/(\text{m}\cdot^{\circ}\text{C})$ was adopted for fused silica, of which the stage and probe are made. The correction for the CLTE was found to be less than 7% in all cases and for a noncritical characterisation, the correction may not be necessary. The average value for the corrected CLTE is $6.1 \mu\text{m}/(\text{m}\cdot^{\circ}\text{C})$, which has an excellent agreement with the value for the boron-free E-glass fibres found in the literature [21]. The average value of 760°C is obtained for T_g and T_g for boron-contained E-glass is said to be near 700°C [22]. T_g can be thought of as a useful indicator of the approximate temperature where the supercooled liquid converts to a solid on cooling. The measured values can be affected by the heating rate as shown in Figure 3.

The measured T_g increases as the heating is accelerated due to increased thermal lag between the actual sample temperature and the reading. However, it is not expected that the CLTE would follow the similar trend. The dependence of CLTE and T_g can be both well

fitted by a quadratic function, which give CLTE=6.1 $\mu\text{m}/(\text{m}\cdot^{\circ}\text{C})$ and T_g=759°C when the heating rate was extrapolated to zero. These values are almost identical to those obtained at 5°C/min.

In terms of general glass forming process, the definition of characteristic temperatures (e.g. T_g) is associated with viscosity of glass forming melt. One of the techniques for the viscosity measurement involves fibre elongation method, where a thick fibre needs to be drawn from an existing bulk glass and is then heated at a constant rate (e.g. 5°C/min), while the fibre is under a constant tensile force, F_f . The fibre elongation rate, dL_f/dt , is then recorded during testing and it is related to the viscosity of the melt, η , by the expression:

$$\eta = \frac{L_f F_f}{3A_f (dL_f/dt)} \quad (7)$$

where L_f and A_f are the fibre original length and cross-sectional area. Fibre area is calculated through $A_f=\pi D_f^2/4$, where D_f is the fibre diameter. It can be seen that the TMA procedure developed in this study essentially share the same concept with the fibre elongation method. Therefore, the results obtained from the TMA procedure could also be used to estimate the viscosity by rearranging Equation (4) in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta &= \frac{L_f F_f}{3A_f (dL_f/dt)} = \frac{F_f}{3A_f} \left/ \left(\frac{dL_f}{L_f dT} \frac{dT}{dt} \right) \right. \\ &= \frac{F_f}{3A_f \alpha_f K} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where α_f is the CLTE of the fibre under F_f at T and K is the heating rate in the measurement. For the TMA run in Figure 2, $F_f=15 \text{ mN}$ (including the load resulting from the weight of the lower sample holder), $D_f=17.1 \mu\text{m}$,

$K=5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, and $\alpha_f=2.7 \text{ mm}/(\text{m}\cdot^{\circ}\text{C})$ at T_g . According to Equation (5), $\eta=9.5\times 10^{10} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ is obtained at T_g . This value is approaching to the magnitude of $10^{11.3}$ established for the viscosity of the glass forming melts at glass transformation temperatures for bulk glass [22].

3.2 length contraction and Young's modulus

Another important aspect of thermal behaviour of the glass fibre is related to structural relaxation at elevated temperature, which was referred to as thermal compaction by Otto[15]. The term emphasises a global structure rearrangement into a more compact configuration, which has a distinct difference than the annealing of massive glass containing residual thermal strains. The recent studies on the hyperquenched glass (e.g. glass fibre) have reported that there may operate two types of structural relaxation when glass fibres are subject to heat-treatment below T_g [16-18]. One is anisotropy relaxation related to local structure arrangement and the other is entropy relaxation dominated by the motion of larger network entities. Both structural changes could create the potential for the axial length shrinkage. However, it is probably the latter that dominates any measurable length contraction. The anisotropy relaxation, on the other hand, has been used to account for the strength decay of heat-treated glass fibres [18]. Figure 4 presents the isothermal length change of glass fibre as a function of time and the results were corrected for the length change associated with the testing fixture by blank run. Below 300°C , the "noise-to-signal" ratio in the TMA was found to be too big to result in any direct observation of length reduction over a prolonged period of time. Above 600°C , the length contraction was overtaken by the creep effect. Despite this limitation, the results in Figure 4 clearly show that there is a significant decrease of the fibre length within the timescale of the measurement at temperatures as low as 300°C .

Based on the study on $7 \mu\text{m}$ E-glass fibres, Otto showed that a length decrease could become effective even just above 100°C [15]. It is obvious that the length contraction is a function of temperature and time. At each temperature in Figure 4 the fibre length changes with the time in a logarithmic fashion, which agrees with the observation made by Otto. It is also noticeable that there seems to be much greater effect of the temperature on the isothermal length change between 300°C and 400°C than the next 100°C interval especially after the initial short time (e.g. 30 minutes) of heat-treatment. This might imply that the creep effect could also be present in the length change obtained at 500°C . The results in Figure 4 indicate that on an atomic scale there must exist very high internal forces, which are able to drive the structure reconfiguration when the fibre is heated up to some critical temperatures. At these temperatures, the viscosity is lowered enough for the internal forces to be effective and the structure begins to rearrange itself into a more compact form, which leads to a decrease of the internal stresses and an increase of the viscosity. Consequently the structural relaxation at a given temperature becomes self-damping and the resulting length contraction gradually dies off after a long period of time as shown in Figure 4. From the energy point of view, a very high level of potential energy must be stored in the glass network during extremely rapid cooling since the structural configuration of glass fibres at room temperature actually represents the state at some higher temperature, which is usually characterised by the fictive temperature. The increase of temperature provides the network with energy and reduces viscosity at the same time. Once enough energy is added in the system and viscosity drops sufficiently, the cooperative motion of the network will become available and bulk structure arrangement will take place to lower the potential energy and reduce the extent of nonequilibrium in hyperquenched glass fibres.

It is expected that the structure relaxation is likely to alter the physical properties of glass fibre such as density, refractive index, and Young's modulus. Figure 5 shows a series of stress-strain curves obtained from a single glass fibre at various temperatures in TMA. It can be seen that stress-strain relationship remains linear for moderately strained glass fibres until the temperature reaches 400°C, at which the nonlinear stress-strain behaviour can be observed. The deviation from the linear relation becomes more significant with further increase of the temperature as seen in Figure 5. Similar situation can be found for the temperature dependence of the slope, which is a measure of Young's modulus. Figure 6 summarises relative changes in Young's modulus as a function of temperature for glass fibres obtained through the developed TMA procedure and the room temperature Young's modulus after heat-treatment at corresponding temperatures. As expected, Young's modulus of glass fibres is inversely dependent on the temperature. The values at all temperatures are based on the original cross-sectional area, which is fractionally different from the actual area taking into consideration of thermal expansion/compaction and plastic deformation at very high temperatures (e.g. > 500°C). Young's modulus becomes ill-defined for glass fibres above 500°C as they become quite viscoelastic and the slope of stress-strain curve changes constantly. However, it can still serve as a good indication of the overall stiffness of glass fibre at those temperatures. The results for the temperature dependence of fibre modulus suggest that there appears to be a transition region around 550°C, after which the decrease of modulus shifts to a faster pace. This transition emerges at a much lower temperature than that obtained from the length changes vs. temperature. This is because the high temperature moduli have been underestimated due to inelastic effect in the force range twice higher than that in the measurement of CLTE. A

dynamic method has been reported to produce higher Young's modulus than a static method for glass above 200°C as the former is known to be more desirable for dealing with viscoelastic properties [23].

In contrast to modulus decay at elevated temperature, it is interesting to see that the stiffness of glass fibres is actually increased after heat-treatment as shown in Figure 6. This observation supports the effect of thermal compaction and also suggests that the length contraction observed in Figure 4 is mainly attributed to entropy relaxation rather than anisotropy relaxation as reducing the degree of longitudinal orientation (if there was any in glass fibre) would have negative effect on the longitudinal modulus. The stiffening in heat-treated glass fibres correlates with the results in Figure 4 since the greater length shrinkage at higher temperature means the more compact structure, which gives higher modulus as shown in Figure 7. It seems that the length shrinkage after 400°C has more significant effect on the increase of room temperature Young's modulus, although the actual length contraction at 500°C might be more than the value obtained in Figure 7 due to the creep effect. This implies that different factors than structural relaxation may become effective at 500°C. It has been said that the water desorbed from E-glass fibres between 500°C and 800°C can be attributed to the diffusion of bulk water from the inner structure [24]. The water in the glass can act as plasticiser and removal of the water from the network may stiffen the structure and contribute to the increase of Young's modulus. An increase of similar magnitude in fibre modulus after heat-treatment was reported in Otto's work [15]. By comparing the modulus obtained from two scenarios in Figure 4, one can see that the trend for the variation in modulus is almost mirror-symmetric with each other, although the magnitude of variation is not always comparable. The lower modulus at higher

temperature indicates greater structure mobility and lower viscosity, which favours structural rearrangement and in turn higher modulus at room temperature after heat treatment.

4. Conclusions

A TMA procedure has been successfully developed with the capability of probing the thermal behaviour of glass fibre. The established protocol was applied to boron-free E-glass fibre and several thermomechanical programmes were carried out over a wide temperature range from 20°C to 900°C. The CLTE of glass fibre showed no temperature dependence below 300°C giving $6.0 \mu\text{m}/(\text{m}\cdot^\circ\text{C})$ for γ -APS coated glass fibre and the value agrees well with the literature for boron-free E-glass fibre. At higher temperatures variations in the fibre CLTE were observed and an abrupt length change in glass transition region allowed for the determination the value of T_g , which was 759°C for the glass fibre used in this work. A simple equation was derived to calculate the viscosity at T_g and the value of $9.5 \times 10^{10} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ was obtained. The results from isothermal measurement showed significant fibre length shrinkage above 300°C. The length contraction was found to follow a logarithmic function of time. This implies that hyperquenched glass fibre tends to undergo structural relaxation when it is heated up to a high temperature. The bulk structure change associated with entropy relaxation led to a more compact glass network, which in turn gave rise to the increased room temperature Young's modulus obtained from glass fibres heat-treated below T_g . In contrast, Young's modulus measured at elevated temperatures showed an inverse relationship with temperature. It follows that there should exist at least two mechanisms, thermal expansion and structural relaxation, which together account for overall thermomechanical behaviour of glass fibres. The former is related to the decrease of Young's modulus at elevated temperatures and the latter is consider to be

responsible for the increase of room temperature Young's modulus after heat-treatment below T_g .

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Fig. 1. Illustration of the TMA setup for the fibre sample

Fig. 2. Typical TMA plot for length change of a single glass fibre as a function of temperature

Fig. 3. Effect of heating rate on CLTE and T_g of glass fibre measured in TMA

Fig. 4. Length change as a function of time and temperature for glass fibres under 10mN static load (solid line: TMA measurement & dashed line: logarithmic regression)

Fig. 6. Relative changes in Young's modulus of glass fibre as a function of temperature (circle) and at room temperature after heat-treatment (square)

Fig. 5. Stress-strain curves of a single glass fibre at different temperatures. Line 1 at 20°C, line 2 at 100°C, line 3 at 200°C, line 4 at 300°C, line 5 at 400°C, line 6 at 500°C, line 7 at 600°C, and line 8 at 700°C. The lines are deliberately spaced with 0.5% strain.

Fig. 7. Correlation between relative changes in Young's modulus and length change for glass fibres

Table 1 TMA results of single boron-free E-glass fibre at heating rate of 5°C/min

Initial sample length (mm)	CLTE within 20°C-300°C ($\mu\text{m}/(\text{m}\cdot^{\circ}\text{C})$)	Corrected CLTE ($\mu\text{m}/(\text{m}\cdot^{\circ}\text{C})$)	Corrected percentage (%)	Tg ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$)
23.01	5.3	5.6	5.7	759
19.74	5.4	5.7	5.6	749
23.25	5.6	5.9	5.4	761
22.28	5.8	6.1	5.2	762
22.64	5.8	6.2	6.9	759
19.39	6.1	6.4	4.9	762
21.91	6.2	6.5	4.8	763